

THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL GAMES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO CHILDREN AT AN EARLY AGE

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Abstract: *This article discusses the importance of educational games in teaching English and the ways how to teach speaking in English to children at an early age through different games. Playing games help young learners increase physical activities as well as mental functions. It gives some information about various games which are used in teaching speaking to young learners.*

Key words: *game, physical activity, mental function, effectiveness, creativity, language skill, young learners.*

According to Harfield , a game is an activity with rules, a goal and an element of fun. He confidently stated that: Games should be regarded as an integral part of the language syllabus, not as an amusing activity for Friday afternoon or for the end of the term. They can be used at all stages of the progression from controlled to free practice, serving at one end of the range as a memory aid and repetition drill, at the other as a chance to use the language freely and as a means to an end rather than an end in itself. They can also serve as a diagnostic tool for teacher, who can note areas of difficulty and take appropriate remedial action. [1]

Game is the child's main and favorite activity, so the child explores the world through games. If foreign languages are taught through games, it will increase the effectiveness of language skills several times. Playing games not only increases a child's physical activity but also helps to shape mental alertness. It also helps a child build self-confidence and build social relationships with others. Therefore, parents and teachers should encourage children to learn through games as much as possible. Piaget (1970) emphasized that children are active learners and thinkers. Children construct knowledge from interacting with the physical environment in developmental stages. Children learn and discover their talents while they are playing different games. It is advisable to use an environment that activates the senses, including active forms of education, such as visual, auditory, kinesthetic. Educational games include playing musical instruments, singing songs, reciting poems, dancing, playing games, watching videos, and making various things with the help of handicrafts. During the childhood period, the child learns languages mechanically, not by understanding. However, given that a child is born with the ability to imitate the sounds of any language, there are many who want to start this process earlier. Studies of the

human brain have shown that the period from birth to the age of three is the most important period of a child's development. It has also been found that the brain of a three-year-old child performs twice as fast and well as an adult. [2]

There are some different educational games which can help children to improve their language skills. If we tell about them, here one of them is given and explained how to play.

Lamp

Door

Window

Carpet

Radio

Chair

Bag

Book

Table

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In this game, young learners should look at the picture and they should match the words with pictures then they ought to draw lines to match. This game help young pupils to broaden an enrich their vocabulary knowledge.

However, we must not forget that it is very important to take into account the child's psychological and language skills. Parents want their child to be mature in all respects, and in many cases, regardless of the child's psychological readiness, try to give him or her assignments in various subjects. In many cases, when parents fail to achieve the expected result, they try to influence their children by reprimanding or comparing them to their peers. But both attempts weaken the child's interest in learning and cause him to lose interest in the world around him. The role of parents and teachers in preventing such tragedies is invaluable. The easiest and most acceptable way to teach a child to think freely, to increase his curiosity and motivation to explore the environment, to enrich the child's imagination, to reveal his creativity. As children play, they put their ideas into practice, test hypotheses, acquire the necessary skills, use their imagination, and explore their own worlds

Games such as color exhibitions, cards, competitions, role-playing games, and making different shapes are one of the most interesting ways to develop children's physical and mental performance. Games with flashcards, competitions, races, and so on, are among the most exciting ways in which children learn. As well as encouraging active learning, they help develop social skills. Educational activities that encourage children to communicate.

Young children learn through their emotions and actions, so learning English should also be done through these same feelings and behaviors. Involving young children in interesting and communicative situations and activities in learning English is a very important factor in mastering language skills. It is especially important to create a variety of interesting and stimulating situations for young children to learn English and to use all available opportunities to ensure that children actively participate in it.

The ability of a teacher to engage a child with gestures and fluent English speech is one of the first and foremost successes in language teaching. In particular, language instructors will be introduced to "Dressing", "Animals and their sounds", "Crafts", "Sing a song and other educational activities are some of the best ways to develop language learning skills in young children. Through these activities, we have the opportunity to expand and develop children's vocabulary, imagination and creative thinking.

"Dressing" is a type of educational activity in which children can be introduced to the fairy-tale heroes of the peoples of the world. When children are introduced to the characters of fairy tales, their costumes are worn and role-playing is done in English, and this activity increases the child's English vocabulary and expands the child's imagination and worldview.

Through this educational activity, children learn and apply words related to human body parts and clothing. Human body parts: head, arms, hands, feet, legs, eyes... Clothes: girls jacket), shirt (boys jacket), t-shirt (t-shirt), shoes (shoes), slippers (slippers), cap (cap), belt (belt), gloves (gloves)... The command is also given with emphasis on body parts. Children also enliven fairy-tale characters in their imaginations, enter the image, and learn to use key words and phrases. It will definitely help learners to develop their speaking skills by listening to English words and composing sentences from memorized words.

Animals and their sounds is an educational activity that introduces the world of animals and insects in English. Children also listen to a variety of stories and tales involving animals. Learning about animals and their movements and sounds in English through colorful pictures of animals is also a fun activity for children.

Pets and domestic animals: dog, cat, duck, cock, hen, chicken, cow...

Wild animals: lion, tiger, wolf, rabbit, fox, snake, deer...

Sing a song. One of the funniest activities for kids. Children tend to sing from a young age, and through singing, children not only gain vocabulary, but

they also learn to pronounce words in tone. One of the most popular types of English songs sung by young children is "Rain, Rain go away." Rain, rain, go away Come again another day Daddy wants to play Rain, rain go away If the educational game is carried out with the help of umbrellas, artificial clouds and artificial fire, children's activity will increase. The effectiveness of the result will increase. It is important to pay attention and encourage the child to learn something in this lesson. Praising successful children for their work also increases their motivation. But psychologists say that praise should be focused on the work done, not on the person. Because if praise is given to a person, it can lead the child to selfishness later. Praise for your work will ensure that any work will continue to be of high quality and fast.

In conclusion, teaching foreign languages to children at an early age will make it easier for them to acquire language skills and abilities. Especially when this knowledge, skills and abilities are absorbed through various games and educational activities, the child develops foreign languages as naturally as his mother tongue. Educational games not only develop knowledge, skills and abilities in the child, but also ensure the child's healthy physical development, mental refreshment, self-confidence and the formation of social relationships with others.

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